

Synthetic pyrethroids for caseworm control, Aduthurai, India, 1984.^a

Insecticide	Formulation (EC)	Dose (g ai/ha)	Damaged leaves before treatment (%)	Mortality ^b (%) after	
				24 h	48 h
Fenvalerate	20	100	81	97 a	91 a
	20	15	81	94 ab	94 a
Cypermethrin	25	80	80	95 a	91 a
	25	60	66	95 ab	94 a
Deltamethrin	2.8	15	82	94 ab	95 a
	2.8	11.25	90	91 ab	92 a
Endosulfan (standard check)	35	500	78	81 b	81 b
Untreated check			86	6 c	5 c

^aMean of 3 replications. ^bIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

caseworm control. IR50 was planted in 40 m².

Pretreatment caseworm damage was recorded on 12 randomly selected hills/plot. Damage between plots did not significantly differ. Results were recorded by counting live and dead larvae 24 and 48 h after treatment.

All pyrethroid treatments were superior to the control and the standard check (see table). Fenvalerate 20 EC sprayed at 100 g ai/ha gave 97% mortality at 24 and 48 h after treatment. *ℓ*

Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

Survey of rodents and rodent damage in deep water rice

S. Somsook, K. Tongtavee, H.D. Catling, T. Keawta, and S. Hongnak, Zoology Section, Entomology and Zoology Division, Department of Agriculture, P. O. Box 9-34, Bangkok 10900, Thailand

We studied rodent activity in several deep water rice fields at Huntra Station, Ayutthaya Province, from Mar 1984 to Feb 1985. One hundred live traps baited with fresh fish were set on 3 consecutive nights at 4-6 wk intervals. In the same fields, stem damage caused by rodents was estimated several times. During the deepest flooding, a large, adjacent field also was sampled.

Rats *Bandicota indica*, *Rattus losea*, and *Rattus argentiventer* were active in the fields. Rat populations were influenced by food availability and floodwater level (see figure). At peak flooding, when all dikes were submerged, we trapped no *R. argentiventer*, but the other species remained active. *B. indica* and *R. losea* continued to live and reproduce in the field. Stem cutting by rats began in Jun and continued through stem elongation at 95 cm water depth. The cumulative seasonal damage probably exceeded 10% of the stems. *ℓ*

Species composition and numbers of rats, Huntra, Thailand, 1984-85. The dashed bars shown for Oct represent rat numbers in an adjacent farmer's field.

Soil and Crop Management

Nitrogen fertilizer efficiency in two major rice soils of Bangladesh

M. I. Ali, principal scientific officer, Bangladesh Institute of Nuclear Agriculture, Mymensingh, Bangladesh

We evaluated N fertilizer efficiency in

Grey Floodplain (Mymensingh) and Red Brown Terrace (Madhupur) soils in Bangladesh in boro, aus, and transplanted aman. BR-3 was planted at both sites. Soil at Mymensingh was a silt loam with pH 6.8, 0.57% organic C, CEC and exchangeable K 9.2 and 0.25

Table 1. Method, time, and rate of N application at 2 sites in Bangladesh.

Treatment ^a	Portion at time of application ^b				Basal application	N rate (kg/ha)	
	Basal	15 DT	30 DT	5-7 DBPI		Boro	Aus/Aman
Control	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
U11	1/3	—	1/3	1/3	B&I	31	31
U12	1/3	—	1/3	1/3	B&I	62	62
U13	1/3	—	1/3	1/3	B&I	93	93
U14	1/3	—	1/3	1/3	B&I	155	124
U21	—	—	1/2	1/2	—	31	31
U22	—	—	1/2	1/2	—	62	62
U23	—	—	1/2	1/2	—	93	93
U24	—	—	1/2	1/2	—	155	124
USG11	All	—	—	—	DP	31	31
USG12	All	—	—	—	DP	62	62
USG13	All	—	—	—	DP	93	93
USG14	All	—	—	—	DP	155	124
U32	—	1/3	1/3	1/3	—	62	62
USG22	1/2	—	—	1/2	DP	62	62
SCU12	All	—	—	—	B&I	62	62

^a U = prilled urea, USG = urea supergranule (1G.), and SCU = sulfur-coated urea. ^b Basal = immediately before transplanting for B&I and immediately after for DP, DT = days after transplanting, DBPI = days before panicle initiation, B&I = broadcast and incorporated during final land preparation, DP = deep point, after pushing into mud to depth of 10 cm.

Table 2. Effect of N application levels and methods on rice grain yield on 2 Bangladesh soils. ^a

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)													
	Mymensingh				Madhupur									
	Boro	Aus	Aman	Mean	Boro	Aus	Aman	Mean						
Control	3.0	e	1.7	h	3.1	c	2.6	2.1	jk	3.0	g	4.4	g	3.2
U11	3.5	de	2.4	fg	3.4	ab	3.1	2.8	hi	3.0	g	5.0	def	3.6
U12	4.5	cd	2.5	ef	3.5	ab	3.5	3.5	fg	3.4	defg	4.9	f	3.9
U13	5.8	ab	2.7	def	3.5	ab	4.0	3.4	gh	3.5	cdefg	5.5	abc	4.1
U14	6.5	a	3.2	abcd	3.5	ab	4.4	5.7	ab	3.8	abcd	5.8	ab	5.1
U21	3.6	de	2.6	ef	3.3	bc	3.2	2.7	ij	3.1	fg	5.4	abcd	3.7
U22	4.0	cde	2.8	def	3.5	ab	3.4	3.5	fg	3.6	abcde	5.2	cd	4.1
U23	4.3	cd	3.3	abc	3.5	ab	3.7	4.1	ef	3.7	abcd	5.5	abc	4.4
U24	6.0	ab	3.4	ab	3.5	ab	4.3	5.3	b	4.1	a	5.5	abc	5.0
USG11	4.2	cde	2.6	ef	3.5	ab	3.4	3.6	fg	3.3	defg	5.4	bcde	4.1
USG12	5.1	bc	2.9	bcde	3.5	ab	3.9	4.7	cde	3.3	defg	5.6	abc	4.5
USG13	6.1	ab	3.6	a	3.5	ab	4.4	4.8	cd	4.0	abc	5.8	ab	4.8
USG14	6.8	a	3.5	a	3.7	a	4.7	6.2	a	4.0	ab	5.9	a	5.4
U32	3.4	de	2.8	cde	3.3	bc	3.2	2.8	i	3.3	defg	5.3	cdef	3.8
USG22	4.3	cd	3.0	bcde	3.4	ab	3.6	4.6	de	3.6	bcdef	5.2	cdef	4.5
SCU12	3.4	de	1.9	gh	3.4	bc	2.9	2.0	k	3.1	efg	5.0	ef	3.4

^a Figures in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different from each other.

meq/100 g soil, and 10-12-2.2 ppm available P-S-Zn. Soil at Madhupur was a silt loam with pH 5.7, 0.50% organic C, CEC and exchangeable K 7.2 and 0.17 meq/100 g soil, and 149-3.1 ppm available P-S-Zn. Time, method, and placement of N fertilizer is in Table 1. Each plot received a basal application of 20-30-20-5 kg P-K-S-Zn/ha.

Grain yield data for both sites are in Table 2. Treatment effects were significantly different in all crops. Usually, yield increased with increasing N application up to 155 or 124 kg N/ha regardless of management.

Single deep point placement of urea supergranules (USG) was superior to equal amounts of prilled urea (PU) applied in 2 or 3 splits in both soils. USG superiority was most pronounced in boro, perhaps because there was greater horizontal and upward movement of N from deep-placed USG in boro, which resulted in better N utilization. Broadcast, split-applied PU may have had higher volatilization losses in the alternate wetting and drying in boro.

Averaging data from three rice crops showed USG performed best at all N doses (Table 2). In both soils, USG at 62 kg N/ha gave the highest grain production per kg N applied. Sulfur-coated urea produced the lowest yields at both sites. *ℳ*

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Effect of crop establishment techniques and seed rate on upland rice yield and weed growth

J. K. Kehinde, Rice Research Program, National Cereals Research Institute, Moor Plantation, Ibadan, Nigeria

Upland rice farmers in Nigeria generally dibble rice seeds at no specific seed rate

after land preparation. To determine the effect of establishment methods on rice yield and weed growth, three crop establishment methods (broadcasting, dibbling, and drilling) were tried at 45, 90, or 135 kg seeds/ha under upland conditions.

The experiment was in a split-plot, randomized block design with three replications. Establishment techniques

Table 1. Effect of seed rate on weed growth and yield of FARO 11, Ibadan, Nigeria.

Seed rate (kg/ha)	Dry weed weight (g/m ²)	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)
45	0.51	1.1
90	0.39	0.9
135	0.35	0.7
LSD	0.05	0.3

^a Drought at flowering stage caused generally poor grain yield.